

The impact of predation in communal sheep flocks in the central Free State Province, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

The communal wool farmers in the Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo area in the Free State Province struggle to improve their livelihoods. Various limitations, such as diseases and parasites, livestock theft, insufficient capital, high feed costs, challenges in marketing, labour constraints, elevated rent expenses, and a lack of professional knowledge, hinder their ability to make significant economic contributions. This study describes the composition of facts and impacts related to predation in communal sheep flocks in the central Free State Province, following a cross-sectional descriptive study using quantitative methods. During interviews, researchers utilised a structured questionnaire to gather quantitative data on small-stock losses over a 12-month period. Data were collected from 351 (28%) of the 1255 communal sheep farmers in the Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo districts. The mean monetary worth of a typically communal farmer sheep flock (mean = 27.36 sheep/farmer) was ZAR 30,861.96/farmer, with an attested reduction of 49.2% of the flock (ZAR 16,103.99/farmer) reported by the farmers. The losses were due to various factors, such as diseases and parasites (37.4%), weather conditions (drought, flood, storms) (22.1%), theft (23.2%), predation (12.1%), disputes over pastures and water (4.6%), and other losses (metabolic disorders and accidents) (0.6%). Loss due to predation in communal sheep flocks was 5.9% of the total flock size. Predation results in the loss of 1.63 per 27.36 sheep in the communal flock. Most farmers did not experience any loss due to predation; in most cases, the loss was not more than five sheep per farmer. There was a statistically significant association between the number of sheep older than 12 months and loss due to predators, $\chi^2(2)=7.83$, $p=0.02$. Participants with more than five sheep older than 12 months were likelier to suffer from predators. Most predation loss was due to unpredictable killings by vagrant domestic dogs. Shepherding played the most vital role in reducing damages due to predators.

KEYWORDS: Depredation, diseases, farming, livestock, predators, theft, vagrant domestic dogs, weather, South Africa

INTRODUCTION

Predation and its consequential impacts bear national ramifications on food security, employment rates and socio-economic deterioration, particularly within small-stock farming in South Africa (Avenant & Bergman 2021). In 2019, the quantifiable expenses incurred due to predation-related losses in small and large livestock reached ZAR 2,710 million and ZAR 511 million, respectively (Van Niekerk *et al.* 2021). The data and their implications for biodiversity and policy formulation predominantly originate from the commercial sector, while the comprehension of predation's influence remains inadequate in communal farming regions of South Africa (Turpie & Aki-nyemi 2018).

A first intensive 5-year study quantified small-stock losses (ZAR 1,218,283) in the sheep flock (854) of the Glen Agricultural College in the Free State Province, South Africa (physically identified losses vs farmer questionnaires). Predation exerted a more significant

impact (72%) on the overall flock size compared to the combined effects of diseases (2%), metabolic disorders and accidents (20%) and livestock theft (6%) (Strauss *et al.* 2021).

The primary predators accountable for most economic losses in agricultural industries are Black-backed jackals (*Lupulella mesomelas*) and Caracal (*Caracal caracal*). Additionally, vagrant domestic dogs (*Canis familiaris*) can substantially harm small livestock, particularly near human settlements (Strauss *et al.* 2021; Van Niekerk *et al.* 2021). According to Strauss (2009), about 70 km west of the Thaba Nchu–Botshabelo area, vagrant domestic dogs, for example, were responsible for the second most significant number of losses, 20% of kills (actual range of 13–26%). In the same study, Black-backed jackals were responsible for 70.2%, and Caracal for 10% of losses.

Limited and reliable predation management information is available from other provinces and communal areas in South Africa (Thorn *et al.* 2013; Constant

2014). A lack of recordkeeping, especially of small stock production and marketing by the communal farmers in the Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo area in the Free State, hinders them from determining their main constraints and makes them vulnerable to fraud. Poor recordkeeping makes it difficult for farmers to track their inventory effectively. This can result in theft or unauthorised livestock sales, as there may be no clear documentation of the number of sheep owned by the farmers and their current status. Various factors, such as diseases and parasites, livestock theft, insufficient capital, high feed costs, challenges in marketing, labour constraints, elevated rent expenses, and a lack of professional knowledge, hamper farmers' ability to make significant economic contributions (Nyam *et al.* 2022).

Animals in poor shape may also be more vulnerable to predation. Low rainfall, through its effect on vegetation, may adversely affect animal health (Levine *et al.* 2008). Diseases, parasites and hostile climatic conditions that contribute to drought and overgrazing are frequent in communal areas in the Free State Province (Van der Westhuizen *et al.* 2020). Sick and vulnerable livestock are at higher risk of being killed, e.g. by Black-backed jackals when predators' other food sources diminish during droughts or overgrazing (Scheiss-Meier *et al.* 2007; Bahta *et al.* 2016; Strauss

et al. 2021). Predation increases when proper herding is lacking, a usual situation in communal farming areas (Lutchminarayan 2014; Hawkins *et al.* 2023).

The impact of predation on the small stock in communal areas in South Africa can devastate both individual farmers and entire communities (Turpie & Akinyemi 2018). Animal, especially small stock, husbandry is a significant source of income and livelihood for many rural farmers and losing only a few sheep can substantially impact their financial stability. Predation misfortune adversities is often exacerbated by many small-stock farmers having limited resources and infrastructure to protect their animals from predators (Lutchminarayan 2014).

This study describes the composition of facts and impacts related to predation in communal sheep flocks in the central Free State Province, following a cross-sectional descriptive study using quantitative methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted in the Thaba Nchu–Botshabelo area of the Mangaung district in the Free State

Figure 1: Map depicting surveyed communities in the Thaba Nchu – Botshabelo area in the Mangaung district in the central and south-eastern parts of the Free State Province, South Africa. (DARD, GIS section, 2023)

Figure 2: Maximum (Tx) and minimum temperatures (Tn) and the long-term average temperatures (9.7 years) from Woonhuis weather station (29.15276°S 26.57214°E; alt. 1269 m a.s.l.) 25 km west of the Thaba Nchu – Botshabelo area. (ARC-NRE 2023)

Province, South Africa (Fig. 1). This region has flat, rolling grasslands, crop fields, isolated sandstone kopjes and mountains. The province is a crop and livestock production area divided into five districts: Mangaung, Xhariep, Lejweleputswa, Fezile Dabi and Thabo Mofutsanyana. However, focus groups for personal communication and training were canvassed in the Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo area in the Mangaung district, where most communal farmers are situated.

The Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo area has 40 communities (59,957 ha grazing area). Among these, 21 (53%)—encompassing 30,182 ha of grazing land featuring various vegetation types, specifically sweet grass veld, sour grass veld, and mixed sour grass veld (Van der Westhuizen *et al.* 2018)—were chosen to ensure a balanced coverage across the study area.

The climate in the area is characterised by cold winters with an average daily minimum of -0.6°C with frost, and hot summers with an average daily maximum of 33.6°C (Fig. 2) (ARC-NRE 2023). The long-term annual rainfall (6 June 2012 – 29 January 2022) for the Botshabelo and Thaba Nchu area is 546 mm (Fig. 3). Most of the rainfall (>70%) is received in the summer from November to March (Fouché *et al.* 1985).

The Free State Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (DAFF 2018) recommends a long-term grazing capacity of 6 ha per Large Stock Unit (LSU) for the Botshabelo and Thaba Nchu area (Meissner *et al.* 1983).

Sampling procedure

The participants were selected via a non-random, purposive, convenience sampling method to reach the communal wool farmers in the Mangaung district. Approximately 1255 small-stock communal farmers were in the Mangaung district (Mocwiri 2022). A sample size calculator (<http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>) was used to determine the sample size to generalise the population. For this study, 295 or more observations have a confidence level of 95%, with the actual value within $\pm 5\%$ of the observation value.

Data collection procedure

Ethical clearance was obtained from the University of the Free State Research Ethics Committee for this project (UFS-HSD2021/0422/21). A structured questionnaire was used in one-on-one interviews to obtain quantitative data on small-stock losses. It took approximately 40 min to complete the 73 questions in the questionnaire. The designed questionnaire captures household demographics, temporary and permanent farm workers, farming experience, the primary source of farming knowledge obtained, small-stock losses, infrastructure, involvement of extension services and input costs. While the survey was in English, all interviews took place in the participants' native languages following the interpretation of the English version. For the interviews, 16 final-year agricultural students at the University of the Free State received training in the questionnaire. Most of these enumerators' home language was Sesotho, but Setswana, isiZulu and

Figure 3: Rainfall data for 2020, 2021 and long-term average rainfall (9.7 years) from Woonhuis (29.15276°S 26.57214°E; alt. 1269 m a.s.l.) weather station 25 km west of the Thaba Nchu – Botshabelo area. (ARC-NRE 2023)

isiXhosa-speaking enumerators were also selected. This enabled the participants, mainly Sesotho-speaking, to talk openly with little restriction. Throughout the data collection phase, supervisors systematically observed enumerators to maintain uniformity, detect outliers, and ensure the precision of the gathered data. The researcher disseminated the questionnaire to respondents and assured them that their data would be confidential.

Extension officers recruited participants by making use of an inclusion criteria list. Small stock comprises wool sheep, dual-purpose sheep, mutton sheep and goats. Although there were about 1255 small-stock farmers, only those farming wool-type sheep were included. Data collection was from November 2021 until February 2022, when most of the ewes would have lambed and the lambs weaned (Strauss *et al.* 2021). The data collected (e.g., farmer demographics, livestock numbers, production, reproduction, losses) included one year's data (2021/2022). Annual direct allocable variable costs (DAVC) (veterinary services and medicine, transport, fodder, fertiliser, farm mechanisation, machinery/equipment hire, repair and maintenance, and operational costs: banking, cell phone, marketing and branding) were also collected and to further the study, additional financial calculations were necessary.

The following direct losses over 12 months were dependent variables in the questionnaire that affected livestock owners and agricultural production in general:

- Disease and parasite: This referred to losses caused by livestock diseases and infestations of parasites that could lead to illness and death of the animals.

Such losses may be due to inadequate veterinary care and/or insufficient preventative measures.

- Drought: This referred to losses triggered by a prolonged period of dry weather, which could lead to a shortage of water and feed for livestock and, in extreme cases, death of the animals.
- Floods: This referred to losses provoked by heavy rainfall or river overflow, which could result in the drowning of livestock, damage to infrastructure and buildings, and loss of crops. Floods can also lead to soil erosion, further affecting agricultural productivity.
- Thunder/Lightning: This referred to losses caused by lightning strikes, which could lead to the death or injury of livestock and damage to buildings and infrastructure. Thunder can also cause stress and anxiety in livestock, affecting their productivity.
- The dependent variables 'drought', 'floods' and 'thunder/lightning' were grouped as losses due to weather conditions.
- Disputes over pasture and water: This variable referred to losses caused by conflicts over access to grazing lands and water sources, which might have resulted in overgrazing, soil degradation and decreased productivity. In most farming communities, extensive grazing areas are unfenced, and sometimes, the sheep flocks of different communities or even small stock from Lesotho get mixed up. Disputes then arise due to differences in ownership (lack of animal identification marks and record keeping) or traditional use rights. The winning party of the dispute gains the sheep and the losing party registers a loss.
- Livestock killed by predators/dogs: This variable reflected losses caused by attacks from predators like the Black-backed jackal, Caracal and vagrant

domestic dogs (de Waal 2009, 2021; Van Niekerk 2010), which could lead to injury or death of livestock.

- Theft: This referred to losses caused by the theft of livestock, which resulted in economic damages for the communal farmers.
- Other: This dependent variable referred to losses caused by other factors not explicitly mentioned above, such as accidents and metabolic disorders (e.g., bloat and acidosis). These losses may be less familiar but significantly impact agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

The following independent (explanatory) variables explain or predict changes in a dependent variable, namely predation:

- The period the communal farmer was practising wool production;
- Monthly income;
- Farm infrastructure (absence or condition of fences and kraals to safeguard the sheep);
- Sheep demographics (flock structure);
- The number of permanent and temporary staff to safeguard the sheep.

Data management and analysis

According to Van Niekerk (2002), using questionnaire survey methods enables researchers to gauge an individual's knowledge, the nature of the information they hold, their values and beliefs, and their attitudes toward the questionnaire topic. When administering a questionnaire survey, participants respond more favourably, and the results are superior to telephonic interviews or mail surveys (Van Niekerk 2002). The questionnaire in this study was created by using the EvaSys software. The SPSS (ver. 29) program processed and analysed the data. Scanned completed questionnaires identified outliers and potential errors. The mean values for missing observations were added to calculate the sum in each category. Average

prices of livestock auctioneers in Bloemfontein, ± 60 km from the study area, were used to calculate the value of communal farmers' sheep flocks. Chi-square analysis was done for descriptive statistics and factors affecting sheep losses due to predation. The results of the analysis is presented below in the form of tables, graphs and text.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structure of the sheep flocks in the study area

Data from 9603 sheep were obtained through interviews with 351 farmers. The minimum number of sheep owned by an individual was 1, while the maximum was 200 (Table 1). The average number of sheep owned by the population was 27.36 ± 32.11 . This number also included lambs (Table 2). Overall, the findings provide insight into the sheep ownership patterns.

Financial value of the communal farmers' sheep flocks

The financial value of the sheep was determined by the categorised flock structure multiplied by the on-the-hoof prices in February 2023 (Myburg 2023) and the average live weights (birth-, weaned- and 12-month weights) for sheep in extensive grazing conditions (Strauss 2009). The total number of sheep in each category was calculated with the average value per sheep to estimate the total collection of all sheep (Table 2).

The total value of 28% of the communal farmers' sheep flocks was estimated at ZAR 10,832,547.45 (ZAR 30,861.96/farmer), with the highest contribution coming from ewes over one year of age (ZAR 5,769,553.50) (Table 2). Therefore, the value for the 1255 communal wool farmers in the Bo-

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the communal sheep flocks.

		Total number of sheep
N	Valid	351
	Missing	0
Mean		27.36
Median		17.00
Mode		4
Std. deviation		32.11
Range		199
Minimum		1
Maximum		200
Sum		9603

Table 2. The financial value (ZAR) of the communal sheep flocks per age category. The assumption is that each category has a uniform distribution of values.

Age category	Mean, kg	Mean, R/kg	ZAR/sheep	Total number of sheep (mean and std. dev.)	Total value, ZAR
0–4 months	4.9	38.50	188.65	(5.6±7.7) 1947	367,301.55
5–12 months	24.6	38.50	947.10	(6.0±8.1) 2094	1,983,227.40
Ewes >1 year	53.0	25.50	1351.50	(12.2±12.6) 4269	5,769,553.50
Rams >1 year	79.0	21.00	1659.00	(4.7±6.2) 1635	2,712,465.00
			av. 1036.56		10,832,547.45

tshabelo and Thaba Nchu area can be estimated at (ZAR 30,861.96 × 1255 = ZAR 38,731,759.80).

The cost of the different farming inputs per year was allocated to all livestock activities. The total LSU for sheep were obtained by multiplying the total number of sheep with the LSU in each category: 0–4 months (0.08 LSU), 5–12 months (0.15 LSU), ewes >1 year (0.17 LSU) and rams >1 year (0.25 LSU) (Meissner *et al.* 1983). Then, the LSUs were calculated for all livestock to determine the contribution in each category (Table 3). The sheep LSU contribution was 34.4 %, which was used to calculate the annual costs/sheep (Table 4).

Financial implications of losses and mortalities in the communal farmers' sheep flocks

The annual direct allocable variable cost for communal sheep flocks can be analysed using various components, each contributing a specific percentage to the total amount (Table 4):

Labour refers to expenses associated with hiring and compensating personnel (temporary or permanent farm workers/managers) involved in the management and care of communal sheep flocks. This includes feeding, shearing, general flock maintenance and, most importantly, herding. The labour cost of ZAR 25.33/sheep (15.73 %) was among the highest contributors to the cost per sheep (Table 4) and varied between seasons and communities. The labour cost in our survey was three-fold higher than in a study on the profitability of Merino sheep (casual labour, 5 %) (Geyer & Venter 2015).

Veterinary medicine and services are essential for maintaining the health and well-being of the communal sheep flocks. The component was the highest allocable cost per sheep (ZAR 28.69/sheep, or 17.82 %; Table 4) and included veterinary consultations, vaccinations, medications, dosing and any specialised services required. The cost in this category was the same (17.6 %) in the study by Geyer and Venter (2015) and only slightly higher compared to a similar sheep flock at FSDARD (Glen) (11.9 %) with no extra veterinary cost because state veterinarians

took care of the state-owned sheep (Strauss *et al.* 2021).

Transport (incl. fuel) encompasses expenses associated with moving the sheep and transporting wool and related materials from one location to another. The amount of ZAR 26.40/sheep (16.39 %) included fuel costs (bakkie/tractor), vehicle/tractor maintenance, and other transport-related expenses, and was the third highest allocable cost per sheep (Table 4).

Fodder cost represents the expenses incurred to feed the communal sheep flocks. This includes purchasing or producing hay like lucerne, planted pastures, and supplementary feeding: maize, licks, pellet concentrates and mineral salt. Only a few pastures (primarily oats) and maize are self-produced to assist with fodder flow. The amount of ZAR 26.98 (16.75 %) was the second-highest allocable cost per sheep (Table 4). Geyer and Venter (2015) indicated that feeding cost was 58 % of the total DAVC, i.e. significantly higher than the feeding cost (16.75 %) reported in our survey. Communal farmers depend primarily on the government assistance, especially fodder, which explains the marked difference.

Machinery/equipment hire, repair and maintenance incurred expenses of ZAR 5.26/sheep (3.27 %) associated with the rental, repair and maintenance of machinery (e.g. sheep shearing) and equipment (e.g. wool press, dosing gun) used in communal sheep farming (Table 4).

The other allocable costs like shearing (ZAR 17.07/sheep, 10.62 %), operational costs (ZAR 7.50/sheep, 4.66 %), farm mechanisation (ZAR 15.05/sheep, 9.34 %), fertiliser (ZAR 4.54/sheep, 2.82 %), and marketing and branding (ZAR 3.94/sheep, 2.62 %) also contributed to the total of ZAR 163.40/sheep (Table 4).

The financial loss in sheep flocks was substantial, amounting to ZAR 5,652,500.51 (ZAR 16,103.99/farmer) (Table 5). As most farmers could unfortunately not ascribe losses in specific age classes to certain causes, the average sheep value of ZAR 1036.56 and ZAR 160.75 cost/sheep (Tables 2, 4) was used to cal-

Table 3. Total Large Stock Units (LSUs) for communal farmers' livestock in Thaba Nchu and Botshabelo area. Calculation of different categories according to Meissner *et al.* (1983).

Description	Livestock number	LSUs	%
Sheep	9603	1604	34.4
Cattle	2962	2962	63.5
Goats	610	98	2.1
		4664	100

Table 4. Annual direct allocable variable costs (ZAR) for communal sheep flocks (2021–2022).

Description	Annual cost (9603 sheep)	Cost per sheep	% of total cost
Labour	243,198.95	25.33	15.73
Veterinary medicine and services	275,497.35	28.69	17.82
Transport (including fuel)	253,503.25	26.40	16.39
Fodder*	259,062.39	26.98	16.75
Fertiliser	43,559.03	4.54	2.82
Farm mechanisation	144,485.26	15.05	9.34
Machinery/equipment hire, repair & maintenance	50,513.39	5.26	3.27
Operational: banking, cell phone	72,086.29	7.50	4.66
Marketing and branding	37,831.40	3.94	2.62
Shearing **	163,959.00	17.07	10.62
Total	1,543,696.31	160.75	100

* Planted pastures, supplementary feeding, e.g. lucern, maize, licks, pellet concentrates and mineral salt.

** This included shearer, wool-handler, and classer for only rams, ewes and lambs 5–12 months.

culate the total financial losses in Table 5. The financial implications in the category diseases and parasites (ZAR2,114,449.46) were significantly higher in all categories of losses like theft (ZAR1,308,659.83), weather conditions (ZAR1,252,386.26) and predation (ZAR683,664.01).

Total losses in communal farmers' sheep flocks

The number of losses due to various factors such as diseases and parasites, extreme weather, disputes over pasture and water, predation, theft, metabolic disorders, and accidents totalled 4721, equivalent to 49.2 % of the total sheep (Table 5).

The highest percentage of losses was attributed to diseases and parasites (37.4 %), followed by weather conditions (droughts, floods, storms) (22.1 %), theft (23.2 %) and predation (12.1 %) (Fig. 4). During the study period (2021/2022), above-normal rainfall was recorded for both 2020 (763 mm) and 2021 (738 mm) (Fig. 3). The abnormal differences between the maximum and minimum temperatures, e.g., in July 2021 ($T_x=23.5$, $T_n=-5.1$), together with below-average rainfall (March – July 2021) and the above-average rainfall (August 2021 – Jan 2022) (Figs 2, 3), can explain the high number of losses to diseases and parasites and to weather conditions (Fig. 4). Losses

due to disputes over pastures and water (4.6 %) were relatively low. However, the financial value of the loss (ZAR261,013.58; Table 5) was still substantial. It could affect the well-being of communal farmers tremendously. A lack of recordkeeping and animal identification also contributed to losses due to disputes over pastures and water when livestock gets mixed up between communities and with livestock from Lesotho. In comparison with other studies by Strauss *et al.* (2021) in the central Free State, other losses (metabolic disorders and accidents) were relatively low (0.6 %; Fig. 4). The majority of communal farmers (58 %) did not engage in recordkeeping practices, while 29 % maintained partial records, and only 13 % maintained detailed records. Consequently, the reported losses might exhibit a potential bias; nevertheless, poor maintenance of documentation significantly influenced communal farmers' management practices and long-term sustainability.

Strauss *et al.* (2021) indicated that lamb losses due to predation were up to 81.6 % of lambs born, and post-weaned losses were 18.6 % of the total flock size over nine years. According to Viljoen (2015), lamb losses due to predation on the National Wool Growers Association monitor farms were also a staggering 46 %, with 89 % occurring before weaning age. Although losses due to predation (5.9 %, or

Table 5. The total financial implication (in ZAR) of losses and mortalities in the surveyed communal sheep flock (9603 sheep).

Losses	Number of losses (% of total flock)	1036.56 av./sheep + 160.75 cost/ sheep	Total
Diseases & parasites	1766 (18.4 %)	1197.31	2,114,449.46
Weather conditions (drought, flood, storms)	1046 (10.9 %)	1197.31	1,252,386.26
Dispute over pasture and water	218 (2.3 %)	1197.31	261,013.58
Predation	571 (5.9 %)	1197.31	683,664.01
Theft	1093 (11.4 %)	1197.31	1,308,659.83
Other losses: Metabolic disorder and accidents	27 (0.3 %)	1197.31	32,327.37
Total losses	4721 (49.2 %)		5,652,500.51

ZAR683,664.01; Table 5) in sheep flocks were still enormous, they were markedly lower than those in commercial sheep flocks (up to 13 %, amounting to R2.34 billion (Turpie & Akinyemi 2018)) but comparable to losses of 2.98–7.35% due to predation on farms in Central Karoo (Conradie & Natrass 2017).

The losses caused by predation were 1.63 per 27.36 sheep (Table 6), the average flock size per farmer, representing a loss of 5.9% (Table 5). While this remains a considerable loss, most farmers (61.3%) reported no losses due to predation. Most losses were no more than five sheep per farmer.

Figure 4: Attributes of sheep losses reported by 351 communal farmers in the Central Free State expressed as a percentage of the total losses.

The Black-backed jackal was responsible for only a few losses, and no losses to Caracal were reported. However, vagrant domestic dogs were responsible for most of the damages, contradicting findings from other studies in South Africa, where the Black-backed jackal was responsible for over 70% of the losses (Strauss *et al.* 2021).

Most sheep were lost due to diseases and parasites, with 69% of participants indicating some loss and most (39%) indicating a loss of 1–5 sheep during the preceding 12 months. Loss due to predators was the fourth contributing factor (following weather and theft), with 36% of participants experiencing loss due to predators and most (31%) indicating a loss of 1–5 sheep during the preceding 12 months.

Although stock theft could have substantial financial implications, most farmers did not experience it (Fig. 4). Unfortunately, if the stock theft syndicates operate in a specific area, they can eliminate the entire communal sheep flock. This happened in the Springfontein community, where three farmers lost all their sheep to organised crime groups.

In 2022, 38,000 livestock theft cases were reported in the Free State Province, of which 21.6% were from the neighbouring towns next to the Lesotho border (Louw 2023). Springfontein community in the Thaba Nchu district is a bare 30km from the Lesotho border. However, criminal syndicates do not continuously operate from Lesotho. Many stock theft losses occur more profoundly within the South African borders. Sheep are the working capital of the communal farmers; therefore, the capital needs to be replaced when stock theft occurs (NSTPF 2015). Many communal sheep farmers indicated that they were selling their livestock to ensure some income instead of losing everything. Although other losses were more remarkable, selling the only source of income would cause serious financial problems for the farmer, the entire community, and unemployment in the Free State Province.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics for factors affecting the loss of sheep in communal flocks.

		Diseases and parasites	Weather conditions	Disputes	Predation	Theft	Other losses
N	Valid	351	351	351	351	351	351
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		5.03	2.98	0.62	1.63	3.11	0.08
Median		3.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mode		3	0	0	0	0	0
Std. deviation		5.609	4.896	2.291	2.767	6.121	0.475
Range		21	21	21	21	21	3
Minimum		0	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum		21	21	21	21	21	3
Sum		1766	1046	218	571	1093	27

Key: 1=0, 2=1–5, 3=6–10, 4=11–20, 5=21+

Table 7. Factors affecting the loss of sheep due to predation.

		Losses due to predators				p-value
		No		Yes		
		n	%	n	%	
Period practising wool production	Five years or less	107	53 %	55	44 %	0.09
	More than five years	94	46 %	71	56 %	
Monthly income	ZAR3330 or less	146	74 %	92	75 %	0.74
	More than ZAR3330	52	26 %	30	25 %	
Number of sheep 12 months or younger	None	29	14 %	16	12 %	0.15
	1–5	150	74 %	86	68 %	
	More than 5	24	11 %	25	20 %	
Number of sheep older than 12 months	None	16	8 %	5	4 %	0.02
	1–5	139	68 %	75	59 %	
	More than 5	48	24 %	47	37 %	
Condition of farm fences/ kraals	Working condition	124	61 %	86	68 %	0.22
	Not in working condition/absent	79	39 %	41	32 %	
Number of workers (temporary and permanent)	No workers	100	49 %	72	57 %	0.08
	1 or 2 workers	78	38 %	34	27 %	
	More than 2 workers	25	12 %	21	17 %	

Causes of predation losses in communal farmers' sheep flocks

Chi-square analysis showed a statistically significant association between the number of sheep older than 12 months and loss due to predators, $\chi^2(2)=7.83$, $p=0.02$. Participants with more than five sheep older than 12 months were likelier to experience loss due to predators (Table 7).

Strauss *et al.* (2021) indicated that kraaling was one of the successful non-lethal methods to mitigate predation. In the present study, the condition of the farm fences and kraals had no significant ($p>0.05$) influence on reducing losses due to predation. Most losses were due to vagrant domestic dogs. Almost every household had dogs and could not predict when

those dogs or stray dogs would cause losses irrelevant to the conditions of the fences and kraals, their farming experience and monthly income. Safeguarding the sheep against predators by temporary or permanent workers evidently influenced the scale of this damage. The farmers indicated that where losses did occur, 57% of them were associated with no farm workers. When labourers were appointed—1 or 2 workers, or more than two workers—the losses due to predation decreased markedly, by 27% and 17%, respectively (Table 7). The lessen predation losses to mesopredators could be attributed to improved shepherding. A recent study indicated that predation losses were five-fold lower when shepherding was implemented compared to areas where shepherding was not part of the farmer's management practices (Hawkins *et al.* 2023). Conradie and Piesse (2015)

argued that investing in more supplementary fodder, better genetics and more labourers would also increase sheep productivity. Unemployment is an acute issue in rural areas in South Africa. Employment opportunities in communal farming are essential as they help alleviate poverty and reduce inequality, particularly in areas with few other job opportunities (Leibbrandt *et al.* 2010; NAMC 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

The financial assessment of communal farmers' sheep flocks in the Botshabelo and Thaba Nchu area reveals valuable insights into the assets and losses incurred in this agricultural context. The estimated total financial value of 28 % of the communal farmers' sheep flocks, amounting to ZAR 10,832,547.45 highlights the economic significance of this sector. This equates to an average value of ZAR 30,861.96 per farmer, with a substantial contribution from ewes older than one year (ZAR 5,769,553.50). Furthermore, the overall financial estimation for the 1255 communal wool farmers in the specified area is ZAR 38,731,759.80. This figure underscores the economic importance of communal sheep farming in the region.

Acknowledging the significant financial losses of ZAR 5,652,500.51 (ZAR 16,103.99/farmer) is crucial. The inability of most farmers to attribute losses in specific age classes to causes due to poor record-keeping highlights the complexity of assessment and alleviation of losses in communal sheep farming. Applying an average sheep value of ZAR 1,036.56 and ZAR 160.75 cost/sheep to calculate the total financial losses provides a standardised approach, enabling a comprehensive overview of the financial impact.

Examination of predation losses in communal sheep farming reveals noteworthy challenges and potential mitigating factors. The findings indicate that predation—with an average loss of 1.63 sheep per 27.36 in the communal sheep flock, which translates to a 5.9 % loss per farmer—poses a significant concern. Despite this, 61.3 % of farmers reported no losses due to predation, emphasising variable experiences within the community. Moreover, most losses reported were relatively modest, with most farmers indicating no more than five sheep lost. Interestingly, vagrant domestic dogs were identified as the primary predator, with some incidents due to the Black-backed Jackal, whereas no losses were attributed to Caracal.

Statistical analysis demonstrated a significant association between the number of sheep older than 12 months and predator-induced losses. Farmers with more than five sheep older than 12 months were found to be more susceptible to predation losses. Additionally, a noteworthy observation emerged regarding the impact of farm workers on predation

rates. Instances where losses occurred, were frequently associated with a lack of farm workers, with a marked decrease in predation losses: two-fold when one worker was appointed and three-fold when two or more. This suggests that the presence of farm workers may effectively reduce predation losses through enhanced shepherding practices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study underscores the imperative for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to address economic losses faced by communal sheep farmers in the Botshabelo and Thaba Nchu area. The highest direct allocable variable costs for the communal farmers' sheep flocks is animal health, but the highest losses also occur in this category. Sustainable economic viability in communal sheep farming can be achieved by enhancing management practices and disease control strategies, mainly through cost-effective measures like bulk purchase of vaccines and veterinary medication. Implementation of best practices for sheep management is crucial, bolstering overall household income and mitigating risks associated with external threats such as vagrant dog attacks and stock theft. Communities ought to undertake domestic dog sterilisation initiatives in conjunction with state veterinary professionals to mitigate the proliferation of undesirable puppy births, thus preventing potential killings by vagrant domestic dogs in the future. Furthermore, it is recommended that communities enforce a prohibition on deploying inadequately trained dogs for hunting purposes. Such untrained dogs indiscriminately target and eliminate various wildlife, posing not only a significant threat to local livestock but also jeopardising biosecurity on a broader scale.

The integration of additional labourers, whether from family or the community, is recommended to assist in the comprehensive management of the sheep flock, thereby fortifying the sector against unforeseen challenges. This scientifically grounded assessment provides a robust foundation for informed policy decisions and targeted interventions, contributing to the region's long-term sustainability of communal sheep farming.

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REFERENCES

- ARC-NRE. 2023. *AgroMet*. Pretoria: Agricultural Research Council – Natural Resources and Engineering.
- AVENANT, N.L. & BERGMAN, D.L. 2021. Introduction. *Indago* **37**: i–ii.
- BAHTA, Y.T., JORDAAN, A. & MUYAMBO, F. 2016. Communal farmers' perception of drought in South Africa: Policy implication for drought risk reduction. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* **20**: 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2016.10.007>
- CONRADIE, B. & NATTRASS, N. 2017. The robustness of self-report data on predation: A comparison of two Karoo surveys. *African Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics* **12**(3), pp. 217–229. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/pdf/10.5555/20173314610>
- CONRADIE, B. & PIESSE, J. 2015. Productivity benchmarking of free-range sheep operations: Technical efficiency, correlates of productivity and dominant technology variants for Laingsburg, South Africa. *Agrekon* **54**(2): 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03031853.2015.1065186>
- CONSTANT, N.L. 2014. *A socio-ecological approach towards understanding conflict between leopards (Panthera pardus) and humans in South Africa: Implications for leopard conservation and farming livelihoods*. PhD thesis. Durham, UK: Durham University. <https://etheses.dur.ac.uk/10807>
- DAFF [DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE FORESTRY AND FISHERIES]. 2018. *Long-term grazing capacity map for South Africa*. *Government Gazette* **41870**: 17–31.
- DE WAAL, H.O. 2009. Recent advances in co-ordinated predator management in South Africa. *Merino Focus* **2009**: 44–46. <https://merinosa.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/predator.pdf>
- DE WAAL, H.O. 2021. Predation management in South Africa – historical milestones. *ALPRU – Occasional Paper* (University of Free State, Bloemfontein) **4.2**: 1–640.
- FOUCHÉ, H.J., DE JAGER, J.M. & OPPERMAN, D.P.J. 1985. A mathematical model for assessing the influence of stocking rate on the incidence of droughts and for estimating the optimal stocking rates. *Journal of the Grassland Society of Southern Africa* **2**(3): 4–6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02566702.1985.9648004>
- GEYER, A. & VENTER, J.L. 2015. Profitability of the merino sheep. *Merino Focus* **2015**: 60. <https://merinosa.co.za/focus-2015>
- HAWKINS, H.J., MINNIE, L., VAN NIEKERK, H.N., DE WAAL, H.O., BALFOUR, D. & KERLEY, G.I.H. 2023. Shepherding is not a shot in the dark: evidence of low predation losses from the Northern Cape province of South Africa. *African Journal of Range & Forage Science* **40**(4): 373–384. <https://doi.org/10.2989/10220119.2022.2156610>
- LEIBBRANDT, M., WOOLARD, I., MCEWEN, H. & KOEP, C. 2020. *Employment and inequality outcomes in South Africa*. Cape Town: Southern Africa Labour and Development Research Unit, University of Cape Town. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:18421633>
- LEVINE, J.M., MCEACHERN, A.K. & COWAN, C. 2008. Rainfall effects on rare annual plants. *Journal of Ecology* **96**(4): 795–806. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2008.01375.x>
- LOUW, M. 2023. Sheep rustlers driving Free State farmers out of business – and police seem different. *Daily Maverick*, 20 February 2023. <https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2023-02-20-sheep-rustlers-driving-free-state-farmers-out-of-business-and-police-seem-indifferent> (accessed 14 September 2023)
- LUTCHMINARAYAN, K. 2014. *Predation impacts on livestock in a communal area of Namaqualand, Northern Cape, South Africa*. BSc thesis. Cape Town: University of Cape Town. <http://hdl.handle.net/11427/12926>
- MEISSNER, H.H., HOFMEYER, H.S., VAN RENSBURG, W.J.J. & PIENAAR, J.P. 1983. *Classification of livestock for realistic prediction of substitution values in terms of a biologically defined Large Stock Unit*. Technical Communication (South Africa, Department of Agriculture and Fisheries) no. 175. Pretoria: The Government Printer.
- MOCWIRI, B.S. 2022. *Mangaung Metro wool commodity*. Bloemfontein: Free State Department of Agriculture and Rural Development.
- MYBURGH, T. 2023. Bloemfontein weekly average auction prices. *Tobie Myburgh afslaers*. <https://www.facebook.com/p/Tobie-Myburgh-Afslaers-100063528551661> (accessed: 21 February 2023)
- NAMC [NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL MARKETING COUNCIL]. 2022. *The smallholder market access research report*. Pretoria: National Agricultural Marketing Council. https://www.namc.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/SHMA-Research-Report_2021-22.pdf
- NSTPF [NATIONAL STOCK THEFT PREVENTION FORUM]. 2015. *Manual for the prevention of stock theft. The farmer's guide to the prevention and handling of stock theft*. 1st ed. Pretoria: Agri Connect (Pty) Ltd. <https://www.elsenburg.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Stock-theft-manual.pdf>
- NYAM, Y.S., BAHTA, Y.T., ODUNIYI, O.S. & MATTHEWS, N. 2022. Smallholder sheep farmers' perception of production constraints and competitiveness strategies in South Africa. *Scientific African* **16**: e01192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e01192>

- SCHEISS-MEIER, M., RAMSAUER, S., GABANAPELO, T. & KÖNIG, B. 2007. Livestock predation—Insights from problem animal control registers in Botswana. *Journal of Wildlife Management* **71**(4): 1267–1274. <https://doi.org/10.2193/2006-177>
- STRAUSS, A.J. 2009. *The impact of predation on a sheep enterprise in the Free State Province*. MSc(Agric.) thesis. Bloemfontein, South Africa: University of the Free State. <http://hdl.handle.net/11660/1702>
- STRAUSS, A.J., AVENANT, N.L. & DE WAAL, H.O. 2021. The impact of predation on Merino and Dorper sheep flocks in the central Free State Province, South Africa. *Indago* **37**(1): 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.38140/00679208/indago.v37.a7>
- THORN, M., GREEN, M., SCOTT, D. & MARNEWICK, K. 2013. Characteristics and determinants of human-carnivore conflict in South African farmland. *Biodiversity and Conservation* **22**(8): 1715–1730. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-013-0508-2>
- TURPIE, J.K. & AKINYEMI, B.E. 2018. The socio-economic impacts of livestock predation and its prevention in South Africa. In: Kerley, G.I.H., Wilson, S.L. & Balfour, D. (Eds), *Livestock predation and its management in South Africa: A scientific assessment*. Port Elizabeth: Centre for African Conservation Ecology, Nelson Mandela University, pp. 53–81. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371760991>
- VAN DER WESTHUIZEN, H.C., MOHLAPO, T.D., DE KLERK, J.D., MAJOLA, S.E., SNYMAN, H.A. & NESER, F.W.C. 2020. Reproduction performance of beef cattle before and after implementing a sustainable grazing system in a semi-arid grassland of Southern Africa. *South African Journal of Animal Science* **48**(1): 112–121. <https://doi.org/10.17159/2413-3221/2020/v48n1a530>
- VAN DER WESTHUIZEN, H.C., SNYMAN, H.A. & FOUCHÉ, H.J. 2018. Sustainable veld management guidelines for the Free State. *FSDARD Research Periodical* **1**: 27–59.
- VAN NIEKERK, H.N., BAHTA, Y.T. & DE WAAL, H.O. 2021. A review and estimation of the financial implications of livestock predation in South Africa. *Indago* **37**: 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.38140/00679208/indago.v37.a2>
- VAN NIEKERK, H.N. 2010. *The cost of predation on small livestock in South Africa by medium-sized predators*. MSc (Agric.) thesis. Bloemfontein: University of the Free State. <http://hdl.handle.net/11660/2000>
- VAN NIEKERK, P.D.P. 2002. *Product development as part of a positioning strategy for the hunting industry in the Eastern Cape*. DTech thesis. Port Elizabeth: Port Elizabeth Technikon. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/145053160>
- VILJOEN, N. 2015. Train for gain. *Wool Farmer* **3**(6): 28–29. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC182280>